

**FORCED-RESPONSE MEASUREMENTS AND CFD-ANALYSIS OF HIGHER VIBRATION
MODES IN A 2.5-STAGE AXIAL COMPRESSOR RIG**

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ABSTRACT

Forced-response predictions of resonance vibration stresses for higher vibration modes are still a challenging task in compressor design. There exist many papers in literature on this important topic, but usually only few lower vibration modes are investigated.

At the last ISUAAAT-conference in 2018, a two-part paper was presented with first results on the influence of acoustic modes on forced-response for a limited range of performance conditions in a 2.5-stage modern compressor rig which was set up at the Institute of Jet Propulsion and Turbomachinery at RWTH Aachen. The present paper is a continuation of the previous work and additional results are presented. Overall, three different stagger angles of the Inlet-Guide-Vane and three different backpressure levels were tested for the two blisk rotors, resulting in 140+ resonance crossings. For each crossing, several CFD calculations were performed with four different solver settings, resulting in about 600 CFD calculations. The large number of resonances allows some statistical evaluations of the results.

In addition to the evaluation of vibration stress levels and aerodynamic damping, 2D-flow field measurements upstream of the rotor 1 are presented and compared with CFD.

Keywords: Forced-Response, Higher vibration mode, CFD, Tip-timing measurements

NOMENCLATURE

EO	Engine Order
HB	Harmonic-Balancing
IGV	Inlet Guide Vane
m	modal mass

n	normal surface vector
p	pressure
S/G	Strain-gauge
t	time
W_{aero}	aerodynamic Work
x	Mode shape, axial position
Λ	Aerodynamic damping
Λ_{exc}	Aerodynamic excitation
ω	frequency

1. INTRODUCTION

Forced-response predictions of resonance stress levels for higher vibration modes are still a challenging task in compressor design. At the last ISUAAAT-conference, a two part paper was presented with first results from the 2.5-stage compressor rig [1], [2]. After a short literature survey on forced-response, the steps for comparing measurement results with analytical analysis are explained.

In chapter 2 and 3, these steps are then applied to the forced-response analysis of the compressor rig.

1.1 Literature survey

This survey can only give a short overview of the existing literature which has become quite extensive during the last years. Each of the papers listed below has an own list with further references.

One of the first forced-response calculations with an Euler code is from Berthillier et al. [3]. They used cylinders of different diameter and quantity and measured the excitation of the downstream compressor blisk by using strain gauges. Only results for the first torsional mode are shown. In spite of several uncertainties, they achieved reasonable stress predictions.

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One of the first blade forced response simulations, taking mistuning into account and with comparison to experimental data was performed by Seinturier et al. [4]. Two different cases are compared. One is a single research rotor whereas the second one aims to represent a more realistic compressor. Two approaches are used for the CFD: one is using Euler equations and the second one uses RANS. Mainly Euler equations are used due to the lower computational cost although it was shown that the results are less accurate than with the RANS model. For the research rotor, just one resonance crossing was investigated and the comparison with experiments was good. For the realistic compressor, three crossings with higher modes were investigated and large differences between prediction and measurements were observed.

Miura et al. [5] studied the forced-response of rotor shock-waves onto the upstream inlet guide vane. One resonance point of the 10th IGV vibration mode was investigated. The analytical results are overpredicted by a factor of about 2. The differences between them seem to depend on the accuracy of the strain gauge measurements since it is not easy to measure the high order mode accurately. Besides that, the inconsideration of the mistuning effect when evaluating aerodynamic damping may be one cause of the difference.

In another paper, Miura et al. [6] tackled a very challenging task of forced-response predictions over several blade rows. Again, only one (lower) mode at one resonance crossing was investigated. The prediction is ~40% lower than measurements.

Hedge et al. [7] studied the forced-response of the second rotor in a 3.5-stage compressor rig. Here, mode 2 and 3 were investigated. Various CFD-setups were tested. The predicted modal force depended on the number of rows included in the CFD-model.

In addition to frequency response functions FRFs, 2D-flow fields from 5-hole-probes for two performance points were presented. The CFD-prediction of the flow field did not match well with the measurements.

In a further paper from Hedge et al. [8], the influence of the hub cavities on forced-response were investigated. Including the cavity flow the comparison between calculation and measurements showed better agreement.

Kovachev et al. [9] investigated low-engine-order excitation of lower vibration modes for a radial turbine test case. They used a non-linear harmonic frequency domain method to calculate the forced-response excitation coming from the inlet volute and the guide vanes. They obtained a quite good agreement between measurements and calculations.

A very recent paper from Maroldt et al. [10] presented results from a 1.5-stage compressor rig for three lower vibration modes with a variation of the vane stagger angle circumferentially. They found that the Harmonic-Balancing method including transition modelling gave good results compared to tip-timing vibration measurements as long as there is no flow separation. Otherwise, time-domain computations are recommended.

1.2 Challenge of Forced-Response Predictions

In Figure 1, the steps for comparing analytical results with measurements of vibration stress are shown in detail for linear cases where the energy method can be used.

For the aerodynamic calculations the steady 3D-flow field including all blade rows of the component is the basis. This already depends on the quality of the inflow conditions and the geometry representation. Flow features like shocks, separation zones and corner stalls depend on the mesh quality and the chosen models for turbulence and transition.

FIGURE 1: CHALLENGE OF FORCED-RESPONSE PREDICTIONS

On the structural mechanics side, the Finite-Element-model of the excited blade is the basis for a modal analysis with the resulting modal displacements and modal vibration stress. The interaction of the blade with the disc may have a significant influence on the modeshape depending on the excited nodal diameter (e.g. in a veering region).

For the energy method, two separate unsteady calculations are performed. The first one uses a moving mesh approach where the CFD mesh is deformed according to the modeshape in order to determine the aerodynamic damping.

Usually, a single blade row is cut out of the whole computational domain. But if cut-on acoustic Tyler-Sofrin-modes are present, they may have an influence on the aerodynamic damping. In reference [10] a change of up to 20% is reported for the aerodynamic damping in a multi-row environment.

The second calculation is the forcing calculation using a frozen mesh. The approach with the least computational effort is to extract the gust boundary conditions from the upstream or downstream exciting blade row and to prescribe them to the single extracted row. Using a frequency domain code, a single blade passage is sufficient. In the presence of acoustic Tyler-Sofrin-modes this approach may lead to wrong results, especially for an excitation from a downstream row.

More complex simulation setups can range from two-row, single passage calculations in the frequency domain up to multi-row 360°-models in the time domain. The computational cost varies over several orders of magnitude. The challenge is always to propagate the correct excitation through the passage.

The most important step is to calculate the aerodynamic work, which is the integral over one vibration period and the whole blade surface for the local product of displacement and unsteady pressure, which comes from the blade movement in the case of damping and from the gust in the case of forcing. If the blade displacement is high, but the unsteady pressure is low, the contribution to the aerodynamic work is negligible and vice versa. Especially for higher vibration modes, this effect may be quite pronounced, resulting in a very high localization of the excitation or damping. The deviation in vibration frequency between calculation and real blade may also be in the order in 5-10%, which leads to another source of error due to a wrong integration time period and an incorrect aerodynamic performance point.

In the next step, the modal vibration stress is multiplied with the aerodynamic excitation and divided by the sum of aerodynamic and mechanical damping, which is rather negligible in the case of a blisk. As all previous calculations are based on the assumption of cyclic symmetry, this results in the “tuned” resonance amplitude.

On the measurement side, input from the Finite-Element-analysis is needed in order to determine the vibration stress from the measured signals from tip-timing and/or strain-gauges. If there is a dependence of the modeshape on the nodal diameter this has also to be taken into account in this step. Individual blade stresses are obtained for all blades (tip-timing) or just a few blades (strain-gauges), which may differ one order of magnitude

due to random mistuning. Thus, in order to make a comparison with the tuned (cyclic symmetry) vibration stress amplitude, a further step is necessary because the average value of the individual blade amplitudes does usually not correspond with the tuned value. Either, a thorough characterization of the blisk is necessary or a general value for conversion from average to tuned may be used, leading to another error in the order of 10% to 30%.

In a real multi-stage compressor, there may be other uncertainties on top like aerodynamic mistuning or the effect of 3-row-Tyler-Sofrin-modes [14], making predictions and comparisons between calculations and measurements even more challenging, especially for higher vibration modes in a compressor.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Experimental setup

The 2.5 stage rig and the instrumentation has already been described in detail in the previous papers. Thus, only a short description is given here. The compressor is a state-of-the-art design with two blisks, one Inlet-Guide-Vane (IGV) and two stator vanes. The first blisk has intentional mistuning, resulting in twice as many resonance crossings.

The cross section of the rig is shown in Figure 2. At the inlet, the flow enters the flow channel radially and is homogenized in axial direction by several flow directing elements. 360°-traverses have demonstrated that the flow has only little circumferential disturbances when it reaches the CFD-Inlet plane, where appropriate instrumentation provides the necessary input for posttest analysis. The pressure ratio at the design point is ~2. The blue region marks the computational domain in the CFD calculations.

The IGV cannot be moved during the rig operation, but with different locking plates it can be fixed at various flow angles.

After each stator, a traversing plane for 5-hole-probes is located. The rotor blade vibrations are measured with the MTU tip-timing measurement system BSSM developed by Zielinsky and Ziller [12]. At the CFD-Outlet, pressure measurements are performed to obtain the outflow boundary conditions.

FIGURE 2: CROSS SECTION OF COMPRESSOR RIG

Figure 3 shows the normalized Campbell-Diagram of Rotor 1 on the right hand side. On the left hand side, the nodal diameter

map is shown with the engine orders and aliased nodal diameters. The color of the symbols corresponds to the parts of the FE-model (top left) and the size is an indicator of the part's contribution to the strain energy. The downstream wake of the IGV is marked with the blue box and the upstream disturbance is marked with the red box. It can be seen that some of the resonance crossings occur in veering regions which has to be considered in the analytical analysis as well as in the measurement evaluation. Modes 4 to 9 gave a significant response during the measurements and are evaluated in this paper. The modeshapes of the average blade-alone-model are plotted on the right, they may change with nodal diameter.

FIGURE 3: NODAL DIAMETER MAP AND CAMPBELL-DIAGRAM WITH MODESHAPES OF ROTOR 1

For rotor 2, the diagrams look similar, except that this blisk does not have intentional mistuning.

Measurements are performed at three different IGV angles of $+16.5^\circ$, 0° and -40° , which are constant during the whole resonance sweep. The compressor maps for these IGV positions are displayed in Figure 4. Three different operating lines with increasing pressure levels have been tested. The bright green line is the choke line of the compressor rig. The medium green line corresponds to the working line and the dark green line is as close to the surge line (red) as possible without the risk of a surge during a resonance sweep. For $IGV = -40^\circ$, high asynchronous vibrations were encountered below about 80% speed, thus only the sweep at choke conditions was performed.

The blue triangles correspond to the resonance crossings of rotor 1 with the wake of the IGV and the orange diamonds indicate the crossings with the upstream disturbance of the stator 1. The magenta circles represent performance points where 2D-flow traverses are available. For rotor 2, a similar resonance crossings can be located in the compressor maps. The resonance sweeps at choke conditions were done with a constant throttle position of the rig. For the sweeps at higher pressure levels it was not possible to make a complete resonance survey with a constant throttle position with a comparable surge margin. Thus several breaks were made, the throttle was adjusted to a higher backpressure and the survey was continued.

FIGURE 4: NORMALIZED COMPRESSOR MAPS WITH RESONANCE CROSSINGS ROTOR 1 FOR $IGV = +16.5^\circ$ (A, TOP), 0° (B, MIDDLE), -40° (C, BOTTOM)

In Figure 5, the flow fields at 50% span for a 90% speed case is displayed for the three IGV angles. The angle of 0° (case B, middle) corresponds to the design intent of the compressor rig. The angle of $+16.5^\circ$ (case A, Top) is representative for an off-design performance point where the boundary layer thickens on the rear part of the suction side, leading to a significantly increased wake thickness. The angle of -40° (case C, Bottom) is characterized by a separation on the pressure side, leading to a large forcing of the downstream rotor. This flow field may occur in a real multi-stage compressor with closed vanes in the idle region.

Flow fields at a constant axial cutting plane showing the forcing distribution are presented in chapter 3.

FIGURE 5: 2D-FLOW FIELD AT DIFFERENT IGV ANGLES: IGV=+16.5° (A, TOP), 0° (B, MIDDLE), -40° (C, BOTTOM)

2.2 Analytical work

For the calculation of the mode shapes, the free FEM-software CalculiX has been used [17].

The CFD analysis has been conducted with the flow solver TRACE, which is developed at the German Aerospace Center DLR in cooperation with MTU Aero Engines. This code has already been widely used for aeroelastic analysis and many publications are available (e.g. Frey et al. [13]). For the unsteady calculations, several solver options are available. In the frequency domain, a linearized and a harmonic balancing (HB) version can be chosen. In the time domain, a fully non-linear computational scheme is available. Several turbulence and transition models can be chosen. For the present calculations, two setups as shown in Table 1 are used. The setups have already been described in [2] in more detail and are the result of extensive studies at a linear cascade.

It was found during the previous papers that for the IGV angle of 0° setup 3 gave better results. There, also a grid sensitivity study has been presented. From recent experiments in this rig it is also known that transition is present and that setup 3 should be the better choice.

Setup	Turbulence model	Transition model
1	k - ω	[-]
3	SST	γ -Re Θ

TABLE 1: NUMERICAL SETUPS

For each resonance crossing presented in this paper, two steady flow solutions are calculated for both setups with the exact boundary conditions taken from measurements. For each steady solution, one unsteady calculation with the linearized version and one with the harmonic balancing version have been performed, resulting in four CFD calculation for each resonance crossing.

For the linearized calculation, the single row of interest is cut out of the steady flow solution and the excitation is prescribed by using a gust boundary condition. For this type of calculation, the steady flow solution is frozen.

For the excitation calculation with harmonic balancing, two rows are cut out of the steady flow solution, the excited and the exciting (upstream or downstream) row. Here, four harmonics are exchanged between both rows. As also the harmonic 0 is included, the steady flow solution is allowed to change. Acoustic Tyler-Sofrin-modes are included in this type of calculation.

The damping calculation is always performed with the linearized code. Some test calculations with the harmonic balancing method in a two-row setup showed only little difference in aerodynamic damping, but a significant longer calculation time.

As already described in the introduction, the energy method is employed to determine the tuned vibration stress level as shown in Figure 1.

2.3 Measurements

In addition to the standard instrumentation for a safe rig operation, special instrumentation is accessible in the compressor rig. For the presented investigation, tip-timing measurements for blade vibrations and 5-hole-probe flow field measurements in the plane between IGV and rotor 1 are of importance.

For the 5-hole-probes, a study was performed in order to assess the influence of this intrusive measurement technique onto the excitation (Sanders et al., [16]). Flow field values evaluated by pressure probe traverses behind stator vanes do not always accurately represent the undisturbed flow field. For example, for the stator 1 of this compressor, the maximum numerically estimated differences are -3% for the average and -13% for the first harmonic of the Mach number. It should also be noted that close to the hub and tip walls no measurements could be taken.

2.4 Random mistuning correction

Several papers (e.g. [7]) try to model the random mistuning on top of forced-response predictions and compare them with the measured vibration envelope. In the current study, we choose the way to make cyclic symmetry analysis and compare the results with a measured average value which is converted to a “tuned” value for each resonance.

The averaged mistuned response amplitudes are usually not equal to the tuned amplitudes. In literature, an average factor of about $0.75 - 0.9$ is mentioned [11], but it can also be as low as 0.4 . As described in the previous paper, the two blisks of rotor 1 and rotor 2 were analyzed with respect to random mistuning by optical white-light scans. Then a conversion factor for each resonance was determined analytically using a reduced order code with this mistuning distribution as an input [18]. These factors are presented in Figure 6. The average is 0.88 (i.e. the average mistuned response is 12% lower than the tuned resonance amplitude) with a standard deviation of 9% . This fits quite well into the observations in literature.

FIGURE 6: AVERAGE-TO-TUNED CONVERSION FACTOR FOR RANDOM MISTUNING

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In the results section it should be noted that all quantities are normalized due to proprietary reasons.

3.1 Damping analysis

As mentioned above, blade vibrations are measured with the MTU tip-timing BSSM-system. The main purpose of the post-processing is to capture the maximum stress response of each blade during a resonance by a fitting process with one or more oscillators. It is not the aim to accurately determine the damping, which is automatically calculated with the half-power method.

In this project, we looked in detail into the damping evaluations as the (aerodynamic) damping is a very important part within the forced-response process. Figure 7 shows two examples of damping evaluations. The green line is the envelope of all single blade responses and the black line is the fit of the individual blade response. The red horizontal bar is the frequency-spread used for the half-power method. It is evident that the fit in the upper picture leads to a damping which is much too high. The fit in the lower picture gives a reasonable damping. From looking at many evaluations it was concluded that the maximum damping values in a resonance are not trustworthy and that the real damping can be found somewhere between the minimum damping and the median value.

FIGURE 7: EXAMPLES OF DAMPING EVALUATIONS

Figure 8 shows examples of the damping evaluations for resonance crossings for all three IGV angles and pressure levels (CHK = choke, AL = working line, NPG = near stall) for the first rotor with the wake of the IGV for modes 4-9. As the nomenclature is difficult to read in the figure 8-11 it is listed in

Appendix 1 at the end of the paper. The dark blue bars indicate the minimum determined damping, the medium blue colored bars the median value and the bright blue bars indicate the maximum damping, which is not trustworthy.

The red dots correspond to the calculated aerodynamic damping from CFD with a constant value for the assumed mechanical damping of 0.1% logarithmic decrement, which is rather small compared with the aerodynamic damping. In most cases, the calculated damping is in between the minimum and median values. Especially in cases where the spread of the measured damping is very small, the agreement is nearly perfect (e.g. Mode 5 for all three IGV angles).

Calculating a relative error between the analytically determined damping and the median of the measured value for all resonance crossings, an average value of 22% is determined. There is nearly no difference between the different IGV angles or the numerical setup (1 or 3). Thus, it can be concluded that the aerodynamic damping can be predicted with a satisfactory accuracy.

FIGURE 8: NORMALIZED DAMPING COMPARISON ROTOR 1 FOR IGV=+16.5° (A, BOTTOM), 0° (B, TOP LEFT), -40° (C, TOP RIGHT)

3.2 Resonance stress levels

In this section, some selected results are presented. All resonances showed a significant response, so that the presented deviations between CFD and measurements are not due to very small amplitudes. In the following figures, the relative error is presented:

$$Relative\ error = 100 \times \frac{\sigma_{CFD} - \sigma_{exp}}{\sigma_{exp}} [\%] \quad (1)$$

Figure 9 shows the relative error in resonance crossings of rotor 1 excited by the upstream IGV (EO40) for setup 1. The bright red bars correspond to unsteady forcing calculations with the Harmonic-Balancing method, the dark red bars those with the linearized method. On the left hand side, results for an IGV-angle of 0° are presented, in the middle those for +16.5° and on the right for -40°. The overall impression is that for IGV = +16.5° the error is quite small (especially for the HB-method) and that for IGV = -40° the error is very high.

Looking at the same results in Figure 10 for the transitional setup 3 it can be seen that for IGV=0° the error decreases. This was already presented in the previous paper and this was to be expected as transition is present in the rig. The new results for IGV = +16.5° and -40° show the not expected trend that setup 3 leads to higher errors for the calculation of the vibration stress.

FIGURE 9: RELATIVE ERROR WAKE IGV=>R1 EO40, SETUP 1

FIGURE 10: RELATIVE ERROR WAKE IGV=>R1 EO40, SETUP 3

In Figure 11, the results for the disturbance of downstream stator 1 onto the rotor 1 (EO52) are presented. Here, the results are sorted differently with setup 1 in bright purple bars and setup 3 in dark purple bars. The top shows the results for the linearized calculation and the bottom for the HB method.

It can be seen that the error for the linearized calculation is close to 100% for all modes and angles, which means that the linearized approach completely fails in predicting the upstream disturbance. This is due to the fact that the upstream gust contains only a small pressure disturbance. But the main contribution to the excitation comes from the Tyler-Sofrin-modes which are exchanged between stator 1 and rotor 1 and which can only be captured by the HB-method in a two-row configuration. For this method, the error is in the order of +/-50%

with some very good agreements for setup 3 and HB for IGV = +16.5° for mode 7.

Similar observations can be made for the resonance crossings of rotor 2 and stator 1.

Linearized

Harmonic balancing

FIGURE 11: RELATIVE ERROR UPSTREAM S1=>R1 EO52, LINEARIZED (TOP) AND HARMONIC-BALANCING (BOTTOM)

Looking at the overall results, there are resonance crossings where the agreement of the vibration stress between calculation and measurement is perfect while at other conditions and/or other modes the agreement is bad.

For all direct disturbances upstream and downstream of both rotors a standard deviation of the error of about 32% (average error of about 36%) can be determined for the Harmonic-Balancing method. This method is mandatory for calculating the upstream disturbance due to Tyler-Sofrin-modes. But the errors may become quite large in some cases so that forced-response predictions of higher vibration modes still have to be considered with caution and to be verified by measurements.

In chapter 3.1 we have seen that the prediction of the aerodynamic damping is quite good. Thus, it can be concluded that the main source of the deviations can be attributed to the forcing calculation. In the following chapter, a detailed look into the flow field is taken.

3.3 2D-Flow fields

From the many traverses which were conducted only a few selected examples can be shown here. The first one is a traverse for an IGV angle of 0° at a relative speed of 87% on the working line. The flow fields are shown in Figure 12. On the left hand side, the measured (normalized) total pressure is shown, where the y-axis represents the channel height and the x-axis the circumferential angular position. In the middle, the CFD

calculation for setup 1 is presented and on the right-hand side that for setup 3. For the IGV angle of 0° the wake is quite small, which is well captured with setup 3 whereas setup 1 over predicts the wake width significantly. Close to hub and tip walls there are also some deviations, but here the measurements have also to be taken with caution due to a possible influence of the walls onto the measurements.

In Figure 13, the flow data are analyzed in more detail. On the left-hand side the averaged total pressure is shown over the channel height. The green line corresponds to setup 1, the red dashed line to setup 3 and the black line represents the measurements. On the first glance, the agreement is quite good. But for the forcing, the first harmonic of the wake in circumferential direction is of importance. Therefore, a Fourier-decomposition of the signal on a constant radius is performed which is shown on the right-hand side. Here it can be seen that setup 3 agrees nearly perfect with the measurements whereas setup 1 predicts a pressure amplitude which is twice as high.

FIGURE 12: 2D-TRAVERSE TOTAL PRESSURE, IGV=0°, N=87% WORKING LINE

FIGURE 13: 2D-TRAVERSE PRESSURE AVERAGE AND AMPLITUDE IGV=0°, N=87% WORKING LINE

Figure 14 shows the flow field for IGV = +16.5° at 59% speed at the choke line. Here, the wake is already much broader compared with the IGV = 0° case due to the thicker boundary layer on the suction side of the IGV. From the fringe plots it is difficult to say which of the CFD calculations is better. This is revealed in Figure 15, where again the circumferential average and the first harmonic of the Fourier-decomposition is shown. Setup 3 matches perfectly the measured average and setup 1 is slightly higher in the middle of the channel. The first harmonic is under predicted significantly between r/h = 0.2 and 0.9 with

setup 1. Closer to hub and tip the pressure amplitude is too high. Setup 3 matches the measurements well in the upper 20% of the channel, but is much higher than the measurements in the lower part of the channel.

FIGURE 14: 2D-TRAVERSE TOTAL PRESSURE, IGW= +16.5°, N=59% CHOKE

FIGURE 17: 2D-TRAVERSE PRESSURE AVERAGE AND AMPLITUDE IGW = -40°, N=63% CHOKE

FIGURE 15: 2D-TRAVERSE PRESSURE AVERAGE AND AMPLITUDE IGW = +16.5°, N=59% CHOKE

For the IGW-angle of -40° the 2D-plot is displayed in Figure 16 for a speed of 63% at choke. The wake is now very broad due to the flow separation on the pressure side. At a first glance, the simulation results seem very close to the measurements with a slightly better wake shape for setup 3.

The average and first harmonic amplitude of the circumferential distribution of the total pressure, plotted along the channel height show a quite good agreement between measurements and simulations (Figure 17). In agreement with the observation made previously for the wake shape, the first harmonic for setup 3 has a shape closer to the measurements along the channel height than setup 1. Both setups also predict a higher amplitude for the first harmonic which means that the pressure drop in the wake is slightly overestimated.

FIGURE 16: 2D-TRAVERSE TOTAL PRESSURE, IGW= -40°, N=63% CHOKE

FIGURE 18: 2D-TRAVERSE PRESSURE AVERAGE AND AMPLITUDE IGW = -40°, N=100% CHOKE

Figure 18 shows the same plot for another speed of N=100% at choke. The average total pressure is predicted quite well with both setups, but in this case the first harmonic is predicted better with setup 1 than with setup 3.

Looking at other performance points and also at other measurement planes (downstream of stator 1 and stator 2) it can be concluded that the overall flow field can be predicted in a satisfactory quality, but looking into details like the first harmonic of the wake there are still larger deviations to the measurements for both setups. This is only displayed here for the pressure amplitude, but also the phase plays an important role.

In combination with the complex mode shapes of the higher vibration modes this leads to the sometimes quite high errors in aerodynamic work, which is the integral over one vibration period and the whole surface of the product of modeshape and unsteady pressure (amplitude and phase) as shown in Figure 1. It is still the challenge to predict the forcing with a sufficient accuracy for aeroelastic analysis.

3.4 Localization of aerodynamic excitation

During the analysis of the results it was observed that the aerodynamic excitation is often quite localized on the blade surface. An example is shown in Figure 19 for mode 11 of rotor 2 with an upstream wake. The top row shows the forcing calculation and the bottom the damping calculation. The modeshape is the same in both cases. In the case of the damping calculation, the unsteady pressure is generated by the blade motion itself and the damping distribution on the blade surface is shown in the lower right picture.

For the forcing calculation, the unsteady pressure is generated by the upstream disturbance (wake and Tyler-Sofrin-Modes) and is already very localized at the leading edge on the tip and hub region. At the hub region, this does not lead to a contribution to the excitation because there is no blade movement. At the tip trailing edge region with a very high blade displacement there is also only very little contribution to the aerowork because the unsteady pressure is close to zero. This leads to a very high localization of the excitation and makes it prone to errors.

FIGURE 19: ROTOR 2 MODESHAPE 11

In order to quantify the localization a histogram with 100 bins was created and the aerodynamic work was distributed in these bins. One bin corresponds to 1% of the blade surface. The result for the forcing and damping calculation is shown in Figure 20. The high localization of the forcing is clearly seen on the left-hand side. For the damping, the distribution of the negative aerowork is not as localized as the positive aerowork for the forcing.

For a quantification of the localization, the positive aerowork in two percent of the blade surface (2 bins with highest aerowork) is divided by the whole positive aerowork. This definition may be arbitrary, but it makes the resonances comparable to each other. If the positive work is distributed evenly over the blade surface, the value is almost zero. If all the

positive work is concentrated in 2% of the blade surface, the value is 1. For the forcing calculation in Figure 20, the localization is 0.42.

This localization factor was calculated for all resonances and the distribution is displayed in Figure 21. The blue dots represent all resonances (upstream and downstream) whereas the orange dots are only the wake dominated resonance crossings. These latter resonance crossings lead to more localized distributions of the aerowork. Localizations as high as 0.8 were observed.

FIGURE 20: ROTOR 2 MODESHAPE 11 – AEROWORK LOCALIZATION

FIGURE 21: LOCALIZATION OF EXCITATION

Based on these observations the question arose if there is a correlation of high localization and error in vibration stress prediction. For this purpose, a regression plot for the relative vibration stress error from the calculations with the HB-method with respect to the localization parameter as defined above was created, for both setups. The result is displayed in Figure 22 where the blue dots represent the setup 1 data points and the orange dots those for setup 3. From the distribution, no correlation between error and localization can be found as also indicated by the regression lines which are nearly constant.

FIGURE 22: CORRELATION LOCALIZATION - ERROR

4. SUMMARY AND CONCLUSIONS

The results presented in this paper can be summarized and appropriated conclusions are drawn:

- Extensive Forced-Response measurements and posttest-CFD-Analysis of a 2.5-stage compressor-rig were performed for three different IGV-angles and pressure levels, resulting in 140+ resonance crossings.
- It could be demonstrated that the calculated aerodynamic damping compares quite well with experimental results.
- The prediction of the vibration stress level is not as good as for the damping. The standard deviation of the error is 32% of the measured stresses, but there are also some quite large deviations.
- The larger deviations are attributed to deficiencies of the flow solver in predicting the exciting 2D-flow field. More effort is needed in order to properly model the local flow phenomena (wakes and secondary flow).
- The aerodynamic excitation for higher vibration modes can be extremely localized and thus may be very sensitive to various errors.
- The Harmonic-Balancing-CFD-Solver gives overall better results than the Linearized Solver because the physical effect of Tyler-Sofrin-Modes is included.

- The extensive forced-response and flow-field measurements provide valuable test data over the whole compressor map for further improvements in CFD code developments.

Although the investigations which are presented here are very comprehensive, they have only been performed at a 2.5-stage rig. For a real multistage-rig with 8-10 stages, the results might be different as rear stages are much more dominated by secondary flow phenomena.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The investigations were partly supported by the research program LuFo V-1. The work was supported by the Bundesministerium für Wirtschaft und Energie (BMWK) as per resolution of the German Federal Parliament under grant number 20T1303C.

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Appendix 1: Nomenclature of Figure 8-11:

Figure	8B		8A		8C		9 & 10		9 & 10		9 & 10		11		11		11	
IGV-Angle [°]	0		+16.5		-40		0		+16.5		-40		0		+16.5		-40	
Column # (including empty columns)	Performance Point	Nominal Mode # (Mistuned Mode #)	Performance Point	Nominal Mode # (Mistuned Mode #)	Performance Point	Nominal Mode # (Mistuned Mode #)	Performance Point	Nominal Mode # (Mistuned Mode #)	Performance Point	Nominal Mode # (Mistuned Mode #)	Performance Point	Nominal Mode # (Mistuned Mode #)	Performance Point	Nominal Mode # (Mistuned Mode #)	Performance Point	Nominal Mode # (Mistuned Mode #)	Performance Point	Nominal Mode # (Mistuned Mode #)
1	Choke	4 (7)	Choke	6 (11)	Choke	6 (11)	Choke	6 (11)										
2	Choke	4 (8)	Choke	6 (12)	Workingline	6 (11)	Choke	6 (12)										
3	Choke	5 (10)	Workingline	5 (10)	Choke	7 (13)	Near Stall	6 (11)	Choke	7 (13)								
4	Choke	5 (9)	Choke	5 (10)	Choke	5 (9)	Choke	5 (9)	Workingline	5 (10)	Choke	5 (9)	Choke	7 (14)	Choke	6 (12)	Choke	7 (14)
5	Workingline	6 (11)	Near Stall	5 (10)	Choke	6 (11)	Workingline	6 (11)	Near Stall	5 (10)	Choke	6 (11)	Choke	9 (17)	Workingline	6 (12)		
6	Choke	6 (11)	Workingline	5 (9)	Choke	6 (12)	Choke	6 (11)	Choke	5 (9)	Choke	6 (12)	Near Stall	9 (17)	Near Stall	6 (12)		
7	Near Stall	6 (11)	Choke	5 (9)	Choke	7 (13)	Near Stall	6 (11)	Workingline	5 (9)	Choke	7 (13)	Choke	9 (18)	Choke	7 (13)		
8	Workingline	6 (12)	Near Stall	5 (9)	Choke	7 (14)	Workingline	6 (12)	Near Stall	5 (9)	Choke	7 (14)	Near Stall	9 (18)	Workingline	7 (13)		
9	Choke	6 (12)	Workingline	6 (11)	Workingline	8 (15)	Choke	6 (12)	Choke	6 (11)	Choke	8 (15)			Near Stall	7 (13)		
10	Near Stall	6 (12)	Choke	6 (11)	Choke	8 (15)	Near Stall	6 (12)	Workingline	6 (11)	Workingline	8 (15)			Choke	7 (14)		
11	Choke	7 (13)	Near Stall	6 (11)	Near Stall	8 (15)	Choke	7 (13)	Near Stall	6 (11)	Near Stall	8 (15)			Workingline	7 (14)		
12	Near Stall	7 (13)	Workingline	6 (12)	Workingline	8 (16)	Near Stall	7 (13)	Choke	6 (12)	Choke	8 (16)			Near Stall	7 (14)		
13	Choke	7 (14)	Choke	6 (12)	Choke	8 (16)	Choke	7 (14)	Workingline	6 (12)	Workingline	8 (16)			Choke	9 (17)		
14	Workingline	8 (15)	Near Stall	6 (12)	Near Stall	8 (16)	Near Stall	7 (14)	Near Stall	6 (12)	Near Stall	8 (16)			Workingline	9 (17)		
15	Choke	8 (15)	Workingline	7 (13)	Workingline	9 (17)	Choke	8 (15)	Choke	7 (13)	Choke	9 (17)			Near Stall	9 (17)		
16	Workingline	8 (16)	Choke	7 (13)	Choke	9 (17)	Workingline	8 (16)	Workingline	7 (13)	Workingline	9 (17)			Choke	9 (18)		
17	Choke	8 (16)	Near Stall	7 (13)	Near Stall	9 (17)	Choke	8 (16)	Near Stall	7 (13)	Near Stall	9 (17)			Workingline	9 (18)		
18	Workingline	9 (17)	Workingline	7 (14)	Workingline	9 (18)	Workingline	9 (17)	Choke	7 (14)	Choke	9 (18)			Near Stall	9 (18)		
19	Choke	9 (17)	Choke	7 (14)	Choke	9 (18)	Choke	9 (17)	Workingline	9 (17)	Workingline	9 (18)						
20	Near Stall	9 (17)	Near Stall	7 (14)	Near Stall	9 (18)	Workingline	9 (17)	Near Stall	7 (14)	Near Stall	9 (18)						
21	Workingline	9 (18)	Workingline	8 (15)			Near Stall	9 (17)	Choke	8 (15)								
22	Choke	9 (18)	Choke	8 (15)			Choke	9 (18)	Workingline	8 (15)								
23	Near Stall	9 (18)	Near Stall	8 (15)			Workingline	9 (18)	Near Stall	8 (15)								
24			Workingline	8 (16)			Near Stall	9 (18)	Choke	8 (16)								
25			Choke	8 (16)					Workingline	8 (16)								
26			Near Stall	8 (16)					Near Stall	8 (16)								
27			Workingline	9 (17)					Choke	9 (17)								
28			Choke	9 (17)					Workingline	9 (17)								
29			Near Stall	9 (17)					Near Stall	9 (17)								
30			Workingline	9 (18)					Choke	9 (18)								
31			Choke	9 (18)					Workingline	9 (18)								
32			Near Stall	9 (18)					Near Stall	9 (18)								